

INVESTIGATION OF DEFORMATION BEHAVIOUR IN PRESS FORMING OF SADDLE SHAPE U BEAM USING CFRTP LAMINATE AND SHEAR CUTTING BEHAVIOUR

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) is expected to be used as one of the materials of mass-produced products such as automotive. The establishment of the processing method of this material is one of the problems that need to be solved. The forming process we employ includes the preheating and melting of a CFRTP sheet using continuous carbon fibre impregnated fabrics, and its press forming into a U beam shape with a different width for the front and rear sections. The mechanical servo press is used in this study. In addition, to remove unnecessary regions from the formed part, shear cutting is employed. On the top face of the U beam, fibre tows showed buckling deformation induced by the fibre deformation at the side face. However, the fibre tows at the bottom of the sheet was not deformed. In an investigation of the shear cutting behaviour, the clearance of the cutting blades and cutting speed was considered, and the cutting load during cutting was obtained. The cutting speed affects the cutting load, and the cutting load was larger at slower cutting speeds. Cut faces have both sheared and fractured faces, and the ratio of these areas varies with the trim line. The mechanism of shear cutting of CFRTP is discussed in this paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) is expected to be applied to mass-produced automotive products because of its short processing time due to its thermoplastic properties. Correspondingly, the establishment of the processing method is one of the problems to be solved. Among the several processing methods, the most suitable way for short-time processing is pre-heating and melting an impregnated CFRTP sheet, its press forming into the desired shape, and cooling in a mould. We deal with the CFRTP sheet with continuous fibre fabric whereby the fabric is impregnated with PA6, and forming using pressing, in accordance to the process described above. Fibre alignment after forming is one of the key elements related to the mechanical properties of the formed part when continuous fibre is used. In addition, the trimming method after press forming is important for process development. In general, water jet or laser cutting are employed to cut the CFRP [1, 2]. However, these methods are time consuming because the tool must move along the trim line of the formed part. On the other hand, the tool movement in shear cutting is very limited, and less cost is required for equipment, thereby establishing shear cutting as suitable for actual mass-production lines [3, 4].

This paper presents the results of the observation of fibre deformation obtained by forming a U beam with a different width for the front and rear sections, using a continuous fibre fabric CFRTP sheet. The shear cutting behaviour and a discussion of the shear cutting mechanism are presented.

2 METHODS

2.1 Material

The reinforcement of the CFRTP sheet is 3K carbon fibre plain woven fabric, whereby the fabric is impregnated with PA6. Five fabrics are stacked and consolidated. The sheet geometry is shown in Fig. 1, and its thickness is 1 mm. The fibre direction of each layer is the same. This sheet is fabricated by Ichimura Sangyo Co. Ltd. Three sheets are stacked, then pre-heated, and press formed into the U beam shape. Therefore, the thickness of the final formed part is 3 mm.

Figure 1: Blank sheet geometry

Figure 2: Punch geometry

2.2 Press forming

Three stacked CFRTP sheets are heated using infra-red heater up to 320°C, transferred, and placed at the centre of the blank holder. The blank holder is supported at a constant force by the air die cushion. Insulating plates are attached on the blank holders to prevent the resin from unnecessary cooling. The blank holders clamp the sheet at a constant force and the sheet becomes the desired shape as the die descends. The die cushion load was 5 kN, the descending speed of the punch was 100 mm/s, the maximum load applied to the sheet at the bottom dead centre was approximately 250 kN in several examinations, and the die and punch temperatures were at approximately 30°C. After 30 s of maintaining the punch position at the bottom dead centre, the formed U beam was removed from the mould. The press machine is the H1F45 mechanical servo press by Komatsu Industries. During the use of the mechanical servo press, the position of the bottom dead centre in actual forming relates to the load applied to the sheet at the bottom dead centre. The U beam has a different width at the front and rear sections and it looks like a bicycle saddle.

Figure 3: Schematics of press die and punch

Figure 4: Appearance of the U beam

2.3 Shear cutting

After the press forming, unnecessary regions of the U beam are trimmed by the trimming die. The trimming die is set in the servo press. As the die descends, the blank holders hold the U beam, and the cutters cut the U beam along the trim line. Viewing it from its side, the upper cutter is inverted V in

shape, therefore cutting progresses from both ends to the centre of the cutter. The shear slope of the upper cutter is 3/135, the cutting-edge angles of both the upper and lower cutters are 0°. The cutter is made of quenched SKD11. The clearance between the upper and the lower cutter is adjustable in a region of a narrower straight section of the U beam. Except for the clearance adjustable region, the clearance is fixed at 0.3 mm. The cutter descending speed and the clearance are the parameters that identify the cutting condition. In the experiments, 0.1 mm and 0.3 mm for the clearance, and 2 mm/s and 26 mm/s for the cutting speed were selected.

Figure 5: Schematics of trimming die

Figure 6: Cutter shape viewed from the side

3 RESULTS

3.1 Press forming

One of the press-formed U beams is shown in Fig. 7. The surface in contact with the die and punch is a glossy smooth surface. It indicates good contact between the tools and the sheet during pressing.

Viewed from above, the fibre tows along the longer direction deform largely [Fig. 7 (a)]. On the other hand, viewed from the bottom, the fibre tows are straight [Fig. 7 (c)]. The inner structure where the fibre tows deform largely [location A in Fig. 7 (a)] is shown in Fig. 8. While the fibres around the top surface are compressed in the direction along the beam's length, almost no deformation occurs from the middle to the bottom surface. During the period at which the melted sheet is deformed into the desired shape, first, the resin around the bottom surface of the sheet solidify rapidly due to the contact with the cold punch. Then the fibres, which will be the narrower side face of the U beam, bended towards the bottom and those fibres are dragged towards the middle of the U beam due to the difference of the profile length between the top and side faces of the U beam. The dragging motion induces the fibres of the top surface to be deformed in longer direction because the resin around the top surface is still molten at this stage. In addition, scratching owing to the convex corner of the die causes fibres at the side face to slide towards the bottom, and this motion induces the fibres, which are width direction, to deform along the width direction of the U beam. These fibre deformations can be seen in only the two layers of the top surface of the sheet. It is considered that unnecessary fibre deformation deteriorates the mechanical properties of the product.

Figure 7: U beam views from the (a) top, (b) side, and (c) bottom

Figure 8: Inner structure of the fibre deformed region

3.2 Shear cutting

The trimmed U beam is shown in Fig. 9. Neither cracks nor incomplete-cut occur, and cutting was successful along the trim line.

The cutting load diagram and the schematics of the positional relation between the cutter and the formed part are shown in Figs. 10 and 11, respectively. In figure 4, the letter “c” means the clearance and the letter “v” means the cutting speed. Regardless of the cutting conditions, the cutting load increases from the onset of the cutting until the cutter progresses to 1.5 mm. The load then stays

constant, and it subsequently drops sharply. Considering the shear slope of the upper cutter, the cutting load decreases right after the cutter tip reaches the bottom surface of the sheet. Cutting must be finished before the cutter goes through the entire thickness of the sheet.

Regardless of the clearance of the cutter, the cutting load curves were the same. The limited clearance adjustable region shown in Fig.6 may have led to this result. In the slower cutting speed (2 mm/s), the cutting load curves have a peak, and approximately 10 kN more load occurs compared to the faster cutting speed (26 mm/s). It is considered that the resin properties cause this difference since they vary from viscous to brittle in regard to the strain rate.

The comparison of the cut face shapes under different cutting conditions are shown in Fig. 12. The cut face has slanting smooth faces and a rough face. Assuming that the smooth part is formed by shearing and the rough part is formed by fracturing, they can now be called sheared and fractured faces, respectively. The slant of the sheared face was formed by the elastic recovery of the bended sheet during shearing. Unlike the shear cut face of the metal, sheared face also occur at the lower part of the cut face. It is considered that the material property cause this difference. The meaningful difference between these specimens cannot be seen in the cutting conditions covered in this investigation.

The comparison of the cut face shape along the trim line is shown in Fig. 13. The tip of the trim line has a large sheared face, and the ratio of the fractured face increases as the centre of the trim line is approached. We have confirmed that the change rate of this ratio matches well the shear slope of the upper cutter.

Figure 9: Trimmed U beam

Figure 10: Cutting load diagram

Figure 11: Schematics of positional relation between the cutter and the formed part

Figure 12: Comparison of cut face shapes under different cutting conditions

Figure 13: Cut face change along the trim line

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Press forming

In the case of continuous fibre composites, optimising the fibre direction—in consideration of the force magnitude and its direction during actual use—and forming in order to align fibres in accordance to design specifications are very important to satisfy the mechanical properties required. In the case of the U beam presented in this paper, if the reason for keeping the fibres of the bottom face straight along the longer direction of the beam is rapid cooling—caused by the contact with the tool—it is also possible to improve the fibre deformation of the top face by rapid cooling. To prevent the sheet from being scratched by the convex corner of the die, either a low friction coating can be applied on the surface of the tools, or a lubricant layer can be used on both surface layers of the sheet.

4.2 Shear cutting

A discussion of the generating mechanism of the cut face is presented in this section. Figure 14 shows the estimation of generating process of sheared face and fractured face. First, the CFRTP sheet is bended elastically. When the progress of the cutter exceeds certain distance, the shear cutting of the

fibres and the resin starts around the surface of the sheet. Unlike the metal, it is impossible to introduce shear deformation in thickness direction in case of the CFRP because the fibres once cut are not able to be re-bonded to the other fibres. Therefore, the sheared face also occur at the lower part of the formed part. The fibres and the resin at the middle region of the thickness stretched by the progress of the cutter. Those fibres break when the stress exceeds of its limit, and then the fractured face is generated.

Figure 14: Process of generating the cut face

4 CONCLUSIONS

The continuous CFRTP sheet was press-formed into a U beam shape and the fibre deformation was analysed. In addition, unnecessary regions of the U beam were removed by shear cutting under different cutting conditions. The cutting load behavior and the cut face shape were analysed. The cut face had the smooth sheared faces and a rough fractured face. The shear cutting mechanism was discussed. Further investigation for this mechanism should be addressed in consideration of the relations with the cutting load curves or actual observations of the cutting process. Although the cut face was relatively rough, its short processing time and its reduced cost requirement are the key features of this method.

5 REFERENCES

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